

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF MOTOR NEURON DISEASE IN A GERIATRIC PATIENT: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Motor Neuron Disease (MND) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder with poor prognosis. Ayurveda considers such conditions under *Vata Vyadhi*, where therapies like *Basti*, *Nasya*, and *Rasayana* are emphasized. **Objective:** To evaluate the efficacy of Ayurvedic interventions in a geriatric case of MND. **Case:** A 70-year-old male patient presented with progressive neurological decline including weakness, tremors, slurred speech, dysphagia, imbalance, and bilateral leg swelling. MRI revealed mild cerebral atrophy and EMG indicated anterior horn cell pathology. **Intervention:** A 32-days Ayurvedic protocol included *Dasha Moola Parisheka*, *Abhyanga*, *Swedana*, *Matra Basti*, *Pratimarsha Nasya*, and oral medicines. **Results:** Bilateral leg swelling resolved within 4 days. ALSFRS-R score improved from 20 to 25, SF-36 QoL from 41.9 to 54.4, with improvement in speech, swallowing, mobility, and hand grip. **Conclusion:** Ayurvedic management

provided symptomatic relief, functional gain, and improved quality of life in this case of MND. Larger clinical studies are needed.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Motor Neuron Disease, Panchakarma, *Rasayana*, *VataVyadhi*.

INTRODUCTION

Motor Neuron Disease (MND), including Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder with global incidence^[1] 1–2 per 100,000 and prevalence^[2] 4–6 per 100,000. Average survival^[3] is 3–5 years, and modern medicine offers mainly palliative care.

From an Ayurvedic perspective, such neurodegenerative disorders can be correlated with *Vata Vyadhi*, as the predominant clinical features reflect *Vata dosha vitiation*. Classical Ayurvedic texts describe manifestations like *Mamsa Kshaya* (muscle wasting), *Indriya daurbalya* (weakness of sense-motor functions), *Bala kshaya* (loss of strength), *Stambha* (stiffness), *Kampa* (tremors), and *Vakswaropaghata* (speech disturbances), which parallel the features of MND. The root cause is aggravated *Vata dosha* affecting *Mamsavaha* and *Majjavaha srotas*, resulting in depletion of *Dhatu*s and functional decline.

Charaka states: “*Vata*, when aggravated, produces numerous disorders, difficult to cure” (*Charaka Samhita, Sutra 20/11*^[10]). Panchakarma procedures such as *Basti*, *Nasya*, *Abhyanga*, and *Rasayana* are considered central. This case report documents the outcomes of Ayurvedic management of MND with objective measures.

CASE REPORT

A 70-year-old male patient was presented to ITRA hospital (15/08/2025) with 4 years of progressive neurological symptoms: difficulty in walking, imbalance, frequent falls, weakness in upper limbs and lower limbs, difficulty with finger movement, progressive bending of fingers, slurred and slow speech, difficulty in swallowing with choking, and bladder issues due to prostate enlargement. He also had bilateral leg swelling since 8 months.

Detailed Patient Information

Parameter	Details
Age/Sex	70 years, Male
Residence	Rajkot, Gujarat, India
Diet	Vegetarian, Sarvarasa sevana
Sleep	Disturbed at night, occasional day sleep
Weight	49 kg (BMI ~18)
History	COVID-19 (2019), Hypertension (since 10 years)
Current Medications	Telmisartan 40 mg BD Syndopa SR 450 mg ½ BD

	Ecosprin 75 mg + Atorvastatin 20 mg HS
Symptoms	Weakness, tremors, slurred speech, dysphagia, imbalance, finger contracture, bilateral leg swelling

General Examination

Pulse: 68/min, BP: 140/90 mmHg, Temp: 37.5 °C, moderately nourished, vitals stable.

CNS examination

Higher Function

Conscious- Intact

Orientation- Intact

Memory – Intact

intellect – Intact

Speech - slurred/slow.

Sensory Examination

- Superficial 1. Touch- a) Fine-Intact.

b) Coarse-Intact

2. Pain- Intact

3. Temp. – Intact

- Deep- Pressure- Intact

- Cortical Sensation- Stereognosis. – Intact

2-point discrimination. – Intact

Graphesthesia. – Intact

Motor Examination

Muscle Bulk

Upper Limb	Right	Left
10 cm above elbow	23cm	23cm
5 cm below elbow	22cm	22cm
Lower Limb		
10 cm below Knee	31cm	32cm
5 cm above knee	35cm	36cm

Muscle Power

	Right	Left
Upper Limb	+2	+1
Lower Limb	+3	+3

Muscle Tone: Normal**Reflexes**

	Right	Left
Knee	+4	+4
Ankle	+3	+3
Biceps	+4	+3
Triceps	+3	+3
Babinski Sign	Positive	

Investigations

MRI Brain (05/03/2022): mild cerebral atrophy, no infarct.

USG KUB (24/11/2023): prostate 54 cc, post-void 17 cc.

EMG/NCS (29/09/2023): anterior horn cell pathology.

CBC & urine: Within normal range.

Dashavidha Pariksha.

<i>Prakriti</i>	<i>Vata–Pitta</i>
<i>Vikriti</i>	<i>Vata Vriddhi with Mamsa–Majja Kshaya</i>
<i>Sara</i>	<i>Madhyama (Tvak, Mamsa, Majja Sara alpa)</i>
<i>Samhanana</i>	<i>Avara (lean body)</i>
<i>Pramana</i>	<i>Height 165 cm, Weight 49 kg</i>
<i>Satmya</i>	<i>Sarvarasa sevana</i>
<i>Satva</i>	<i>Madhyama Satva</i>
<i>Aharashakti</i>	<i>Avara</i>
<i>Vyayamashakti</i>	<i>Avara</i>
<i>Vaya</i>	<i>Vriddha (70 years)</i>

Intervention

Treatment began on 22/08/2025 and continued for 32 days:

1. *Dashmoola Parisheka* (22–25 Aug 2025): external pouring with *Dashmoola* decoction × 4 days. Result: stiffness reduced, bilateral leg swelling resolved.

2. Matra Basti

- First course (26 Aug–01 Sep 2025): *Kalyanaka Ghrita* 60 ml daily.

- Second course (02–08 Sep 2025): *Mahanarayana Taila* 30 ml + *Kalyanaka Ghrita* 30 ml daily.

Both courses supported with *Sarvanga Abhyanga (Bala Taila)* and *Nadi Swedana*.

3. *Pratimarsha Nasya* with *Shadabindu Taila* (9 Sept –22 Sep 2025): 2 *bindu* in each nostril daily.

4. Internal medicines (22 Aug–22 Sep 2025): *Musta Siddha Jala Pana*, *Eranda Bhrishtha Haritaki* 3 g HS, *Gokshuradi Guggulu* 400 mg 2 BD.

Therapy	Drug/Material	Dose/Procedure	Duration	Ayurvedic Rationale
<i>Dashmoola Parisheka</i>	<i>Dashmoola Kwatha</i>	External pouring, 2 L lukewarm decoction	4 days	<i>Shotha hara, Vata shamana</i>
<i>Abhyanga + Swedana</i>	<i>Bala Taila</i> for massage; <i>Nadi Sweda</i> with <i>Dashmoola Kwatha</i>	Daily whole-body massage + steam	14 days	<i>Snehana</i> , reduces stiffness, improves circulation
<i>Matra Basti</i>	<i>Kalyanaka Ghrita</i> (60 ml); later <i>Mahanarayana Taila</i> 30 ml + <i>Kalyanaka Ghrita</i> 30 ml	Per rectum after meal	14 days	Best for <i>Vata Vyadhi</i> , <i>Rasayana</i> effect
<i>Pratimarsha Nasya</i>	<i>Shadabindu Taila</i>	2 <i>Bindu</i> in each nostril daily	14 days	<i>Urdhvajatrugata Vata chikitsa</i> , supports speech & swallowing
Oral Medicines	<i>Musta Jala</i> , <i>Eranda Bhrishtha Haritaki</i> , <i>Gokshuradi Guggulu</i>	<i>Haritaki</i> 3g HS, <i>Gokshuradi Guggulu</i> 400 mg 2 tab.BD	32 days	<i>Rasayana</i> , <i>Vata anulomana</i> , <i>Mutravaha</i> support

The Patient was advised to follow the strict *Pathya ahara* (~Dietary regimen for the present condition) preferably freshly cooked. He was also asked to refrain from day-sleep and to avoid all the aggravating factors of *vata* and *kapha*. Few mobilizing and stretching exercises were also advised under the supervision of the attendant but were not strictly followed by the patient.

Follow up & Outcome

The patient's clinical progress was assessed using the ALS Functional Rating Scale (ALSFRS), a standardized tool used in MND to evaluate functional capacity. The scale assesses bulbar, respiratory, gross motor, and fine motor functions, with each parameter scored from 0 (worst) to 4 (normal). The maximum possible score is 40.

Baseline assessment revealed a total score of 20, indicating significant impairment. Post-treatment assessment showed improvement with a total score of 25, reflecting enhanced bulbar function (speech, salivation), improved respiratory status (dyspnea reduction), and better gross and fine motor abilities (turning in bed, handwriting).

Domain	Score (Before)	Score (After)
Bulbar: Speech	2	3
Bulbar: Salivation	2	3
Bulbar: Swallowing	2	2
Resp: Dyspnea	3	3
Resp: Orthopnea	4	4
Resp: Insufficiency	4	4
Gross Motor: Turning in bed	1	2
Gross Motor: Walking	2	2
Gross Motor: Climbing stairs	0	1
Fine Motor: Handwriting	0	1
Fine Motor: Cutting food	0	0
Fine Motor: Dressing & hygiene	0	0

RESULTS

Swelling: Bilateral leg swelling resolved after 4 days of *Parisheka*.

Speech & swallowing: Moderately clearer speech; swallowing improved with fewer choking episodes.

Mobility: Walking easier, hand grip improved slightly.

ALSFRRS-R: 20 (BT) → 25 (AT).

SF-36 Quality of Life: Overall mean improved from 41.9 → 54.4.

Deep tendon reflexes of both upper and lower limbs also remained unchanged. No changes were observed in plantar reflex.

DISCUSSION

MND remains a therapeutic challenge in modern medicine due to its progressive and incurable nature. The Ayurvedic perspective provides a valuable approach, where the pathogenesis is linked to aggravated *Vata dosha* causing degeneration of *dhatu*s, particularly *Mamsa* and *Majja*. The condition is considered *Yapya* (manageable but not curable), where treatment aims at controlling symptoms, slowing progression, and improving quality of life.

This case highlights the potential of Ayurvedic management in MND. *Dashmoola Parisheka* resolved leg swelling, consistent with *Shotha hara* properties.

Abhyanga and *Swedana* improved circulation and reduced stiffness. *Abhyanga* with *Bala Taila* improved muscle tone and strength. *Matra Basti* with *Kalyanaka Ghrita* and *Mahanarayana Taila* provided dual benefits: *Ghrita* acted as a *Rasayana* with neuroprotective properties, while *Mahanarayana Taila* promoted strength and rejuvenation. *Matra Basti*, considered *Ardha Chikitsa* (*Charaka Siddhi* 1/25^[11]), provided systemic *Vata* pacification and *Rasayana* effect.

Pratimarsha Nasya with *Shadabindu Taila* played a role in improving speech, swallowing, and higher functions, as described in classical texts. *Pratimarsha Nasya* improved bulbar functions, supported by classical references (*Charaka Sutra* 5/56^[12]; *Ashtanga Hridaya Sutra* 20/12^[13]).

Internal medicines complemented the therapy: *Musta Jala* provided diuretic support and increase appetite, *ErandabristaHaritaki* aided *Vata anulomana*, and *Gokshuradi Guggulu* supported *Mutravaha srotas*.

The objective improvements in ALSFRS-R and SF-36 scores indicate functional and quality-of-life gains. While limited to one patient, this report adds evidence to Ayurveda's role in chronic neurodegenerative disorders.

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CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic management with Panchakarma provided functional improvement and better quality of life in this MND patient. This integrative approach warrants further controlled studies to establish its role in neurodegenerative conditions.

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